

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ABOUT THE TEACHING OF ENERGY MACHINES AND TRANSPORTATION MACHINES APPLIED IN VARIOUS FIELDS OF NATIONAL ECONOMY IN TECHNOLOGY CLASSES

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Abstract

In modern times, the technology subject program (curriculum) serves the development of the technological thinking of students of general education schools, the formation of technological skills in them, and the acquisition of necessary knowledge to continue their education in the next stages. In the article, the structure and operation status of energy machines taught in high school is explained, the types of machines, their importance and how to facilitate human labor are noted. It is also explained in those lessons that transport and power machines play a key role in many heavy and light industries. Thus, the students are given extensive information about the transportation of all the products that are beyond the reach of humans by using these transportation machines in various fields of the National Economy. At a time when radical changes in technologies are taking place at a great speed, teaching the application areas and importance of these technical equipment to students leads to their even more information in this field and the expansion of their technical knowledge. In the research work, the wide application of energy and transportation machines in various fields of the national economy, their areas of use, types, etc. has taken a wide place. The center of attention in the research work is the process of forming the methodical system of mastering the information about energy and transportation machines, their working principles, the contemporary "techno-democratic-informational society" references, the realization of the expected results as a component of the information that should be mastered to the students. The professions and specialties that students will choose in the future, in turn, require the acquisition of new knowledge, habits and skills. In one way or another, the close connection of all fields of the national economy with the science of technology has been shown.

Keywords: Generator, forklift trucks, stator, manual transmission, steam transmission, Lawrence force, electric power, elevators, escalators, electric and internal combustion engine transmission, lifting mechanisms, cranes, hoists.

Relevance of the research topic: The preparation of the growing generation for life and practical activities includes the preparation of qualified professionals according to the demand of the pace of development in our country. This reality is reflected in the "Education Reform Program of the Republic of Azerbaijan".

In the social, economic, and cultural life of our country, a complex program of reforms is implemented in accordance with the challenges of the modern era.

One of the goals of choosing education as a priority direction in this process is to prepare the emerging generation for life from an early age.

Information about technological machines, devices, tools and mechanisms contained in the content of the expected results in the teaching of the subject "Technology" in general education schools, their working principles have an "enabling function" and the formation of a methodical system aimed at its mastery is a "didactic cognitive issue". This issue is related to the broader problem of system formation. The functioning of the system aimed at realizing the expected results in the subject "Technology" makes that problem permanent. Therefore, this topic can be considered relevant

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials. In the economic and cultural life of our country, a complex program of reforms adequate to the challenges of the modern era is being implemented. It is known that the formation of the educational space is based on the "man-society-technology (which is becoming adequate to the challenges of the IV industrial revolution)-nature" paradigm, which

is a condition for the human struggle for freedom or the development path towards civilization.

Technology is constantly updating itself and developing. It is a variable event, the invariant is not specific. Therefore, it is possible to encounter a new technological development every day. This development affects a person's life. Innovations and technological development have a positive impact on people's lives. It is already known to all of us that the 20th century was characterized by the rapid development of science and technology, the development of new technologies, scientific and practical innovations, information and communication technologies, and entered history as the information age, the age of science and education in a broader sense. [4;53]

The 20th century is characterized by the rapid development of electrical engineering. Thus, the quantity, size and power of the produced electric machines are continuously increasing, their structural structures are improving and their mass per unit power is decreasing.

Electric machines are one of the most basic elements of electrical equipment widely used in industry, agriculture, transport, military equipment and household in modern conditions. Man uses different machines in his work. The main purpose of their use is to lighten human labor. Power machines include electric power generators. [5;23]

Generators convert mechanical energy into electrical energy. They are used in power plants, various transport devices, cars, airplanes, ships, locomotives, mobile power plants, etc. is installed. In power plants,

they are rotated by powerful steam or hydraulic turbines, and in transport devices by internal combustion engines or gas turbines.

Generators are also used in communication and automatic devices, measuring equipment, etc. they use as a nutrient source. The working principle of all generators is the same. Mechanical energy is used to rotate the shaft of the generator. The transformation is based on the Lorentz force. The Lorentz force describes the force acting on an electric charge when it moves in a

magnetic field. If a conductor moves transversely in a magnetic field, the Lorentz force moves the charges on the conductor along the conductor. The movement of the charge creates a voltage difference across the ends of the conductor. To increase the voltage, they use conductors in the form of loops. In the generator, the rotor rotates relative to the body. When a stator with a magnet on it rotates in a magnetic field, the Lorentz force creates an electric current. The obtained electrical power is equal to the mechanical power.

Modern electrical engineering has achieved great success. New series of electric machines have been developed and the issues of mastering them with high precision are being investigated, new magnetic, winding

and insulation materials are being applied to improve the energy and other indicators of the machine. [6;8]

Motor vehicles need electricity to power their devices, keep the engine running and charge their batteries. Until about the 1960s, motor vehicles tended to use DC generators (dynamos) with electromechanical regulators. Following the historical trend above and for many of the same reasons, these have now been replaced by alternators with internal rectifier circuits.

At present, various types of forklift trucks are used for lifting and lowering loads in enterprises operating in almost all fields of industry. Lifting-carrying machines allow to increase the productivity of the industrial enterprise by automating this type of work, as well as eliminating heavy work related to loading and unloading.

Lifting-carrying machines (LCM) technology has developed very widely and forms the main part of the machine-building industry. These machines are integral and basic mechanical equipment of modern industrial enterprises. Quite rightly they are called "hands of production".

An important task of the QNM course is to learn the means of mechanization in the transport of goods in various fields of industry and agriculture.

The correct selection of lifting equipment is one of the main conditions for the normal and high productivity of production.

The use of lifting transport devices in human life belongs to the ancient historical period. Archeological excavations and constructions of historical monuments that have survived until now show the attempts of people to facilitate the lifting and transportation of loads and to lighten labor-intensive tasks with the help of primitive mechanisms. In the 16th and 17th centuries, a small amount of metal was used in lifting devices. However, starting from the 18th century, metal began to be used in these devices. The development of industry and technology, which began at the beginning of the 19th century, laid the foundation for the development of the lifting transport and machine building industry. In 1827, the first stationary steam crane was developed, and in 1880, a steam locomotive working together with a crane was developed for the first time in Russia. The

vertical steam boiler placed in this steam locomotive also performed the duty of the opposite load. This faucet was a fully rotating faucet. Starting from this period, lifting machines began to develop rapidly. In 1877, the first floating steam crane was built, and in 1880, the cable crane was built. In connection with the discovery of electric transmission at the end of the 19th century, an electric rotary crane in 1885, an electric bridge crane in 1887, and a perfect three-mechanism electric bridge crane were built and put into use in 1889. Starting from the beginning of the 20th century, forklifts and electric drives almost replaced the steam engine.

Internal combustion engines were used in forklifts only in 1895.

There are 3 main periods in the history of the development of lifting machines.

1 - Manual transmission machine.

2 – Steam engine.

3 – Electric and internal combustion engine transport vehicles.

In the development of the material technical base, in the improvement of economic indicators, the role of lifting and transporting machines is great.

Modern technological and automatic flow lines, loading and unloading of inter-shop and intra-shop transport require the application of various types of lifting and transporting machines and mechanisms to ensure the rhythmic and uninterrupted operation of production processes. That is why lifting and transporting equipment has not been an auxiliary tool in production processes, but has become a factor that determines the capabilities of modern productions.

The correct selection of lifting and transporting equipment is a decisive factor for ensuring the normal operation and high productivity of factories. Modern high-performance forklift trucks with high speed and large lifting capacity have been gradually developed over a long period of time. The primary means of mechanization were: supports, rollers and inclined planes. Carrying out large-scale construction works using such mechanization means requires the use of a large number of people. For example, more than

100,000 people have always been engaged in the construction of the Xeonsa pyramid, which has been under construction for more than 20 years. Boom lifts - a type of modern arm cranes - were used to raise water as early as the 22nd century BC.

Forklifts are the main equipment in the field of mechanization of transport work in factories, factories and other industrial enterprises. Lifting and transporting loads is hard physical work. To mechanize this work, lifting transport machines are widely used.

Forklift trucks are given the exact name "Lifting transport vehicles" in the full sense. These machines are not only used to lift loads, but also transport them to certain destinations. So, forklifts are mainly used to lift and transport loads. These are included in the group of vehicles used periodically.

Forklifts are divided into three main groups.

1. Lifting mechanisms

2. Faucets

3. Lifters

The group of lifting mechanisms includes winches, jacks, hoists, manual and electric hoists and birail trolleys.

The group of cranes includes jib cranes, bridge cranes, rail cranes, crawler cranes, tower cranes, cable cranes, floating cranes, etc. includes

The group of elevators includes elevators, elevators and other such mechanisms that lift goods and passengers in vertical and inclined directions.

Machines that lift the load and move it in certain directions are called cranes. Cranes are made in different structures depending on the working conditions. However, despite the variety of construction of cranes, their mechanisms mainly consist of lifting, moving and turning mechanisms. Thus, some are equipped with lifting and two-way movement mechanisms, others with lifting and turning mechanisms, lifting movement and turning mechanisms. Manual cranes are called "hand cranes", and electric cranes are called "electric cranes". In addition to these, there are also cranes that work with a steam engine and an internal combustion engine (railway cranes, tractor and car cranes, etc.).

Cranes are used to mechanize loading and unloading operations in industrial enterprises, construction sites, river and sea ports, railway transport, etc. Lifting cranes load-carrying arrangements provide lifting, short-distance transportation and lowering of loads by means of a vehicle.[2;8]

Hoisting cranes are divided into different types according to the constructions, displacement, type of transmission of mechanisms, degree of rotation and method of fixing.

According to their construction, cranes can be bridge, leveling crane type, arm and self-propelled.

Overhead cranes include bridge, jib, bridge loader-unloader, cable and bridge cranes. Boom cranes include tower, portal and console cranes, and self-propelled cranes include crawler, rail and floating walking cranes.

According to the design of the crane, hook cranes (for lifting various loads), magnetic cranes (for transporting steel and cast iron loads), clamp cranes (for lifting barrels, boxes, bags, etc. loads), traverse cranes (loaders based on traction force air pressure) provided with equipment, can be an automatic loader (for transporting containers).

Şəkil 1.1 Kranlar :a- pnevmotəkərli; b-avtomobildə yerləşmiş

Depending on the type of displacement, lifting cranes are stationary and movable. According to the type of rake device, it can be rail, pneumatic wheel, crawler, rope, walking and floating type.

According to the type of mechanism transmission, cranes are manual, electric, hydraulic, pneumatic, internal combustion engine, steam or combined transmission.

According to the degree of rotation of the arm, the cranes are divided into full-turning, full-turning and non-turning cranes.

Depending on the method of leaning on the crane road, there are support and suspension type cranes. [1;3]

There are also column lifting devices. They help lift construction materials to higher floors in construction sites.

In our modern world, the demand for elevator equipment is increasing day by day. The construction of new high-rise buildings, "skyscrapers" increases this demand and makes elevators indispensable. The first elevator device was created in the 16th century, similar devices were used in ancient Egypt. Elevator devices are updated from time to time and reflect the latest achievements of science and technology today. [11;9]

An elevator is a lifting device. For several centuries, it has been used to transport people and goods from one level to another in a vertical direction. During this period, the elevators have undergone a rich development, improved, reliability and safety have been increased, the control system has been simplified, and the interior (artistic design of the interior) has been beautified. Modern elevators have a perfect design and interior, a high-level electronic control system. Now it is

impossible to imagine modern skyscrapers, magnificent business centers, high-rise residential buildings without elevators. Elevators are usually installed inside the building, in a special basement. In loading (unloading) areas, the warehouse is equipped with automatically opening doors. An elevator is a cyclically moving lift-carrier that lifts and lowers people or goods from one level to another in a cabin moving along vertical guides. Elevators are usually installed inside the building, in a special shaft. In the loading (unloading) areas, the shaft is equipped with automatically opening doors. [12;42]

Fibers can be divided into the following types:

According to the type of transported cargo: Passenger elevators - for transporting people whose total mass is not greater than the lifting capacity of the elevator and small cargo belonging to them. Currently, the

number of elevator modifications and different types of lifting devices is quite large.

Classification by destination: For passengers, for cargo, for cargo and passengers, for hospitals, for cargo platforms, for industry.

Depending on the purpose, there are the following types: Passenger elevators for residential buildings; Passenger elevators for administrative buildings; Passenger elevators for public buildings; Elevators for low-rise buildings (cottages) - elevators with a speed of up to 0.63 m/s can be installed in buildings with up to 5 floors. Hospital elevators are used for the transportation of patients and their accompanying staff in internal transport vehicles in treatment and prevention institutions. Such elevators are operated by an elevator operator. Handicapped elevators are passenger elevators

that are operated by passengers who have lost the ability to move and walk in wheelchairs themselves. Freight elevators. It is divided into the following groups: Conventional cargo elevators - cargo lifting capacity is 250-5000 kg; Guided freight elevators - for transportation of goods and accompanying passengers; Unmanned freight elevators - for transporting goods only. [11;18]

Elevators are divided into 4 main types according to the lifting mechanism as follows:

Hydraulic Lifts

Hydraulic elevators are supported by a piston at the bottom of the elevator that pushes the elevator up. They are used for 2- to 8-story low-rise applications and travel at a maximum speed of 200 feet per minute.

Traction Elevators

Traction elevators are raised by ropes that pass over a wheel connected to an electric motor on top of the elevator shaft. They are used for medium and high-rise applications and have higher travel speeds than hydraulic elevators.

Climbing Elevator

They keep their power devices mostly on electric or combustion engine. Climbing lifts are often used in work and construction sites.

Pneumatic Lifts

Pneumatic elevators are raised and lowered by controlling the air pressure in the chamber where the elevator sits. With simple principles of physics; The difference in air pressure above and below the vacuum elevator cabin transports the cabin as if by air.[8;73]

Transporters also include escalators that carry people.

Escalator

It is a moving staircase – a conveyor transport device for transporting people comfortably and safely in large buildings, hospitals, public buildings, pedestrian crossings, etc. The best advantage of escalators is that the user who is going from one place to another can reach it faster. It is also quite convenient and convenient for the older generations.

Escalators, which have the capacity to carry more people than elevators, are usually used in places where elevators are impractical or in conjunction with them. The escalators, which can be easily installed at the same clearance distance as the stairs, are also manufactured in a weatherproof manner for outdoor use.

The direction of movement (up or down) can always be the same or automatically changed by the staff depending on the time of day. (the system is programmed so that the direction is not changed while the passenger is on the escalator). [10;26]

There are 4 typical forms of escalators:

"side by side or separated by distance" (up and down escalators) often seen in Parallel-Metro stations and multi-level cinemas.

Cross- Commonly used in department stores or shopping malls. By "stacking" escalators going in one direction, the structure minimizes space requirements.

Lots of parallels—Two or more escalators moving in one direction next to one or two escalators moving in the other direction on one bank.

Next to the stairs "Up" or "Down".

According to the Regulations on Health and Safety in the Use of Work Equipment, escalators and stairs must be inspected at least once a year. In addition, it must effectively and safely lift at least 1.25 floors of the declared load, unless otherwise specified in the relevant standards. There should also be a brake system to stop the load and to hold the load in case of danger. [10;71]

The scientific outlook of the future engineer, technician, technologist begins to emerge in high school, and is formed and strengthened in higher school. The importance of the scientific worldview increases even

more during the independent labor process where the young specialist starts working in the industry and makes optimal decisions.

In modern conditions, where scientific and technical progress is organically connected with the advantages of the economy, the importance of secondary education in training specialists with comprehensive knowledge in higher schools is great. [13;54]

Scientific significance of the study: Science acts as the basis of productive forces and has acquired the status of the means of labor, the subject of labor and the joint element of labor power. If knowledge is expressed as a tool for both expanding the scale (quantitatively) and increasing the efficiency (qualitatively) of material

production, then designing advanced technological processes, machines and equipment, and theoretically justifying the perfect organization of production to achieve them is the direct goal of science. It is important that today's student, who will be the expert of the future, be educated in the spirit of loving scientific and social activities, and that his worldview is formed correctly. Scientific outlook is based on scientific knowledge and reasoning.

In the technology classes, the teaching of the application fields of heavy and light industries of the energy machines and transportation machines, the rules of use of the national economy helps to form the scientific worldview of the students, and lays the foundation for growing up as a citizen of the modern "techno-democratic-informational society".

Practical significance of research. In order to regulate the successful and developing environment of students, it is possible to raise the efficiency level of the practical pedagogical activity based on the interpretation of the theoretical and technological directions of the arguments that are considered important and the possibilities of the educational process at different levels of general education. Scientific and technical progress reflects the strengthening development of the interaction between science and technology. This manifests itself in the organization of productive forces, technology, management methods and production. Scientific and technical progress has two forms of development. Productive forces are always developing, techniques, technology and other areas of production are constantly being improved. Qualitative changes are taking place in science and technology, which in turn lead to profound new structures in all production. There comes a time when previous techniques and technology are out of order. At this time, due to the emergence of a completely new type of energy, materials, techniques and technology, and on the basis of gradual changes,

quality leaps occur in the development of production. This is a revolutionary form of scientific and technical progress. Scientific and technical revolution is a component and the highest stage of scientific and technical progress.

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